

A CASE STUDY ON EFFECT OF ROMSHATAN LEPA ON HIRSUTISM

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ABSTRACT

Hirsutism, or the presence of unwanted hair, is a common medical condition that often leads to significant psychological and social distress. It is defined as the growth of excessive, male-pattern terminal hair in women after puberty. The causes of hirsutism may be linked to adrenal or ovarian disorders, exogenous drug therapy, or may remain idiopathic. In recent years, its prevalence has increased, particularly among young women, due to the rising incidence of polycystic ovarian disease (PCOS). *Romshatana Lepa*, a traditional Ayurvedic formulation, is described in classical texts as having potential depilatory properties and is believed to be beneficial in the management of hirsutism. Its topical application in the form of a paste offers a localized and targeted approach for reducing excessive hair growth. *Sharangadhara Samhita* specifically mentions *Romshatana Lepa* for permanent depilation, noting its

significant effect when used appropriately. This paper presents a **case study of a patient with PCOS-associated hirsutism**, where topical application of *Romshatana Lepa* was undertaken. Encouraging results were observed, highlighting its potential as a safe and effective Ayurvedic intervention in the management of hirsutism.

KEYWORDS:- Unwanted hairs, Hirsutism, Romshatan lepa, Depletion of hairs, PCOS.

INTRODUCTION

Hirsutism is a condition marked by excessive growth of terminal hair in women in a male-like pattern, involving areas such as the face, chest, pubic region, buttocks, and thighs. It often presents with cosmetic distress but may also indicate underlying endocrine disorders such as polycystic ovarian disease (PCOS) or adrenal dysfunction. With the rising incidence of PCOS, hirsutism is increasingly encountered in young women. The prevalence of hirsutism is estimated to be **5–10% among women of reproductive age**, though reports vary between **4–11% worldwide** depending on ethnicity and diagnostic criteria. In women with PCOS, the prevalence is considerably higher, affecting nearly **65–75%** of cases.

From a pathophysiological perspective, about 50% of androgens in women originate from the ovaries and adrenal glands, while the rest are produced peripherally. In circulation, 80% of testosterone binds to sex hormone-binding globulin (SHBG), 19% to albumin, and only 1% remains free and biologically active. Within the pilosebaceous unit, testosterone is converted into dihydrotestosterone (DHT) by the enzyme 5- α reductase, which stimulates excessive hair growth.

Conventional management focuses on androgen suppression and hair removal but has limitations such as cost, recurrence, and side effects. Ayurveda offers alternative remedies through depilatory formulations, specifically **Romashatana Lepa**, which is documented in classical texts for reducing unwanted hair.

AIM AND OBJECTIVE

1. To evaluate the clinical efficacy of Romashatana Lepa in reducing unwanted hair growth in women with hirsutism.
2. To assess the safety and tolerability of the formulation.

Case History

- **Patient Name:** XYZ
- **Age-** Female, 22 years
- **Occupation-** Student
- **Chief Complaint:** Excessive coarse hair growth on chin for 2 years.
- **Medical History:** Menstrual cycles irregular since 2 yrs no history of endocrine disorders, not on any hormonal medication. K/c/o PCOS
- **Marital Status-** Unmarried

- **Previous Treatments:** Threading and waxing every 10–15 days, with temporary relief.
- **Psychological Impact:** Patient reported cosmetic distress and reduced social confidence.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Drug Preparation-In Sharangdhara, for permanent depilation Ronshatan lepa has been mentioned.

तालकं- शाण युग्मंस्यात्षट्शाणं शंखचूर्णकम् ।

द्विशाणिक पलाशस्य क्षारदत्त्वा प्रमर्दयेत् ।

कदलीदण्डतोयेन रविपन्नरसन वा।

अस्थापि. सप्तभिलेपे रोम्णां शातनमुत्तमम् ॥ शा.स.लेप प्रकरण, 35

shuddha Hartala Bhasma (1 part) shuddha Shankha Bhasma (3 Part), palash kshara (1 Part) as main ingredients They mix it and gave a Bhavana of kadalikanda swarasa. He stated that by using these lepas depilatory effect is seen . So romshatan lepa is taken with a view to find out efficacious safer, cost effective

METHOD OF APPLICATION

- Patch test performed prior to application.
- A thin layer of the formulation was applied over the chin region for **10 minutes daily for 10 consecutive days**, administered in **three treatment cycles with an interval of 21 days between each cycle**.
- Patient instructed to wash the area with lukewarm water afterward.

Standardization of drug

Sr. No	Name of Test	Result
1	Colour	Buff coloured
2	Smell	Faint odour
3	pH	8.00
4	Loss on drying at 110°C	1.50 % w/w
5	Total Ash	80.00 % w/w
6	Acid Insoluble Ash	9.00 % w/w
7	Water solubility	6.00 %
8	Alcohol soluble	17.00 %

OBSERVATION AND RESULTS

Parameter	Before Treatment	After 10 Days
Hair Density	High	Significantly Reduced
Hair Thickness	Coarse	Finer
Pigmentation/Irritation	None	None
Patient Satisfaction	Low	Improved
Ferriman Gallway Score-	4	1

The patient reported visible reduction in hair density and slower regrowth after the course of treatment.

RESULT

Good Depilation Activity Seen.

Fig – This is the hair growth within 10 days after application of romshatan lepa.

DISCUSSION

- Shuddha Hartala (Purified Yellow Arsenic/Arsenic trisulfide): Known for its Romharana (depilatory) property, it constitutes 1 part of the formulation. Hartala is believed to decrease cellular energy levels and reduce mitotic activity, leading to cessation of hair follicle formation.
- Shuddha Shankha (Purified Conch Shell/Calcium carbonate): Possessing Vilekhana (scraping) property, it forms 3 parts of the formulation. Shankha provides an alkaline medium that facilitates the depilatory action of the preparation.

- Palasha Kshara (Alkaline extract of *Butea monosperma*): Having Ksharana (corrosive) property, it constitutes 1 part of the formulation. This ingredient enhances the depilatory effect by providing an additional alkaline medium.
- Some variations of Romashatana Lepa may include additional ingredients such as Sudha (chalk/calcium), Godanta (a mineral), or Kadali (banana plant) extracts, depending on the specific textual reference.
- In textual reference according to Acharya Sharangdhara for Romshatan Lepa-Kadali Swarasa or Araka Swarasa mentioned as a Bhavana Dravya but we see some patients have Allergic reaction after Arka used that's why better to use kadali swarasa as a bhavana dravya.
- From the above we can draw an inference that the romashatana lepa works by decreasing the cellular energy level and thereby leading to decreased mitotic activity and cessation of hair follicle formation. As mentioned above the shankha and palasha kshara provides the alkaline medium to facilitate the depilation activity of romashatana lepa.

CONCLUSION

The Study demonstrated that Romshatan Lepa exhibited effective depilation activity without any adverse effect. know any adverse effect and efficacy need to do this study on large case.

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